

Shear Behaviour of Cold-Formed Stainless Steel Lipped Channel Sections with Web Holes

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ABSTRACT

Cold-formed stainless steel structural members are increasingly used in infrastructure for their corrosion resistance, aesthetic appeal, and strain hardening. Accurate design methods are crucial for achieving optimal use of stainless steel, given its high cost. In construction, web holes are commonly introduced to cold-formed stainless-steel sections for service installation like pipes, ducts, and cables. The introduction of web holes can significantly weaken the section, reducing its load-carrying capacity, so it must be carefully considered during the design phase. Despite their importance, there are limited studies investigating the shear strength reduction due to web holes in cold-formed stainless-steel sections and assessing existing Eurocode 3 shear design provisions. To address this gap, shear strength data of cold-formed stainless steel lipped channel sections with circular web holes was collected from the literature. The collected data included austenitic and duplex stainless-steel grades and web hole ratios ranging from 0.1 to 0.85. The collected data was used to assess the applicability of current shear design guidelines in the Eurocode 3 (EN1993-1-4) structural design specification. The comparative assessment revealed that the existing guidelines for solid cold-formed stainless-steel sections cannot be extended to cold-formed stainless steel sections with web holes. The comparison revealed that these guidelines are not suitable for capturing the influence of web holes on the shear strength of cold-formed stainless steel lipped channel sections. Therefore, new shear design proposals specifically for these sections with web holes were developed based on the collected data. The proposed shear design guidelines offer more reliable predictions of ultimate shear strength for cold-formed stainless steel lipped channel sections compared to the existing Eurocode 3 (EN1993-1-3) design rules.

Keywords: Cold-formed lipped channels, Stainless steel, Shear strength, Web holes

1 INTRODUCTION

Despite its high cost, cold-formed stainless steel (CFSS) has emerged as an increasingly popular material for a wide range of construction applications. This is mainly because it has many valuable qualities, such as being lightweight, resistant to corrosion, strong, flexible, and having a good appearance (1)(1). When comparing stainless steel to carbon steel, there are several distinct differences. One significant factor is the presence of a chemical element known as chromium. The main reason for stainless steel's corrosion resistance, which turns it into a high-performance construction material suitable for challenging environments and heavily polluted areas, lies in its capacity to leverage the strength and stiffness of ferrous metal alloys in conjunction with chromium. This results in the formation of a firmly bonded chromium oxide shield on the steel's surface, effectively safeguarding it (1, 2). In the case of carbon steel, painting the surface is necessary to

achieve this protective covering. Stainless steels are categorized into five groups: duplex, ferritic, austenitic, martensitic, and precipitation-hardening. Among these, the austenitic and duplex grades are most commonly used in structural applications, offering an outstanding combination of corrosion resistance, formability, and manufacturing capabilities. However, the ferritic stainless-steel group is often favoured due to its relatively lower cost and absence or minimal use of nickel content, while still providing excellent properties akin to those of austenitic and duplex grades (3, 4).

In contemporary construction practices, cold-formed steel sections are employed as load-bearing components, exemplified by their application as floor joists, as depicted in *Fig. 1*. These structural elements often feature web holes of different shapes (circular (5), triangular, square (6), diamond and staggered slotted (7,8)) and sizes, primarily for aesthetic purposes or to accommodate service conduits, as illustrated in *Fig. 2*. However, the presence of these openings leads to notable stress and localized buckling in the web due to reduced web area. Consequently, this diminishes the bending and shear capacity of the members.

Fig. 1. Application of cold-formed sections in floor systems by Clark Dietrich Building Systems (6)

Fig. 2. Different types of web holes in stainless-steel beams (9): a) Circular; b) Triangular; c) Diamond; d) Multiple slots

Numerous researchers have undertaken extensive experimental and numerical investigations into the impact of these web holes on the shear capacity reduction of cold-formed carbon steel sections (5, 10-16). Various calculation procedures and formulas have been adopted to quantify the reduction across different cross-sections and web hole shapes. However, there are limited research available in the literature investigating the influence of web holes on the shear strength of CFSS sections. Lawson et al. (9) conducted a series of nine experiments on cold-formed austenitic and lean duplex stainless steel lipped channels featuring wide web holes, which were subjected to combined shear and bending loads. Based on the findings of this study, a methodology was proposed for estimating the local stress

in the vicinity of the circular web holes. Ishqy et al. (1) conducted parametric finite element analysis to explore the shear strength of CFSS lipped channels with circular web holes. This study led to the formulation of sets of equations for shear strength reduction factors. Yousefi et al. (3) investigated the impact of circular web holes on the shear strength of cold-formed ferritic stainless steel unlipped channels without straps, focusing on placement of web holes at mid-span or offset to the applied load. Experimental tests involving 21 shear tests on pair channels were conducted, followed by finite element analysis. The findings highlighted the shortcomings of the existing shear strength reduction factor equations, prompting the development of new design equations. However, it is important to note that Ishqy et al. (1) and Yousefi et al. (3) investigations did not offer any attempt to evaluate the suitability of current Eurocode 3 shear design provisions for stainless steel (17). Based on the experimental tests and finite element analysis results, Dissanayake et al. (18) proposed improved shear design guidelines for CFSS lipped channels, while Gatheeshgar et al. (19) proposed improved shear design provisions for cold-formed carbon steel sections in accordance with the Eurocode 3 design standards. However, there is a lack of extensive research regarding the evaluation of Eurocode 3 shear design provisions for CFSS lipped channels with web holes.

The main purpose of this paper is to formulate shear design guidelines for cold-formed stainless steel (CFSS) lipped channel sections with circular web holes. This is essential because the existing shear design provisions in Eurocode 3 (17) are considered insufficient to account for the influence of web holes. Using shear test and finite element analysis (FEA) results derived from previous studies, an extensive shear strength database for CFSS lipped channel beams with circular web holes has been compiled. This database serves as the basis for evaluating the effectiveness of the current shear design provisions. Ultimately, more accurate estimation of ultimate shear strength for CFSS lipped channel sections featuring web holes are proposed in line with Eurocode 3 (17) shear design provisions for CFSS sections.

2 DATA COLLECTION

One significant challenge of this study is the limited amount of research conducted to determine the impact of circular web holes on the shear strength of CFSS sections. Additionally, there is a scarcity of available experimental data. Since the focus of this study is the effect of circular web holes on the shear strength of CFSS lipped channels, the work carried out by Ishqy et al. (1) primarily serves as a data collection effort. Ishqy et al. (1) conducted a comprehensive parametric analysis on CFSS lipped channels with circular web holes subjected to predominant shear failure.

Figs. 3 and 4 depict the numerical models developed by Ishqy et al. (1), demonstrating configurations both without and with web holes. These models were employed for validation against shear test results. The setup utilized a conventional 3-point bending arrangement with a reduced shear span (aspect ratio equals to unity), designed to minimize the influence of bending moments and promote shear-dominated failure in the specimens. The FEA employed considered the condition of flanges being restrained by straps. This method was used because the condition without flanges restrained by straps could lead to a combined effect of shear failure and flange distortion occurring closer to the loading region. This phenomenon primarily arises due to the unbalanced shear flow within the lipped channel section. The presence of flange distortion has the potential to lead to a reduction in shear strength of up to 11% (10).

Fig. 3. Shear failure of CFSS lipped channels without web holes: Experiment (18) and FEA (1)

Fig. 4. Shear failure of CFSS lipped channels with web holes: Experiment (11) and FEA (1)

Ishqy et al. (1) generated FEA models containing two distinct stainless-steel grades: the austenitic grade 1.4301 and the duplex grade 1.4462, in accordance with EN 1993-1-4 (17) standards. The parametric models they developed incorporated variations in web height for lipped channels, web thickness, stainless-steel grade, and web hole ratios. The web hole ratio denotes the proportion of web hole height to clear web height. The web hole ratios ranged from 0.1 to 0.85, enabling an examination of the impact of web hole sizes. In total, 180 FEA results were collected from Ishqy et al.'s (1) investigation to assemble a comprehensive dataset. The dataset included 18 results with not web holes. The summary of this collected dataset is provided in *Table 1*.

Table 1. Summary of collected data from Ishqy et al. [1]

Lipped channel (mm×mm×mm)	Thickness (mm)	Stainless steel grade	Web hole ratio	No. of data
150×65 ×15	1, 2, 3	EN 1.4301 EN 1.4462	0, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8, 0.85	60
200×75 ×18	1, 2, 3	EN 1.4301 EN 1.4462	0, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8, 0.85	60
250×75 ×20	1, 2, 3	EN 1.4301 EN 1.4462	0, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8, 0.85	60

3 EUROCODE 3 SHEAR DESIGN PROVISIONS FOR CFSS SECTIONS

3.1 Current EN1993-1-4 (17) shear design rules

EN1993-1-4 (17) is grounded in the effective width method, employing a traditional approach to categorize cross-sections into different behavioral classes. This classification hinges on assuming the behavioural class of the slenderest element, while also considering the impact of material characteristics, support conditions, and loading patterns. The guidelines for managing shear effects introduced in EN1993-1-4 (17) should be checked in conjunction with the guidelines provided in

EN1993-1-1 (20) and EN1993-1-5 (21). According to EN1993-1-4 (17), shear resistance of cross-section can be estimated using Eq. (1).

$$V_{b,Rd} = V_{bw,Rd} + V_{bf,Rd} \leq \frac{\eta f_{yw} h_w t_w}{\sqrt{3} \gamma_{M1}} \quad (1)$$

In Eq. (1), the variables are defined as follows: $V_{b,Rd}$ represents shear resistance, $V_{bw,Rd}$ denotes contribution to shear resistance by web, $V_{bf,Rd}$ denotes contribution to shear resistance by flange, f_{yw} stands for yield strength of web, h_w refers to web depth between flanges, t_w represents thickness of the web and γ_{M1} is the partial factor. It is recommended that η be taken as 1.2, as per the guidelines in EN1993-1-4 (17).

Shear resistance of the web can be estimated using Eq. (2), where χ_w represents the reduction factor for web shear buckling, and the corresponding values for webs with fixed end-posts are provided in Eq. (3). It is important to highlight that the contribution to shear resistance from the flange is minimal, particularly in the case of lipped channels (18). As a result, the contribution from the flange was not taken into account in this study.

$$V_{bw,Rd} = \frac{\chi_w f_{yw} h_w t_w}{\sqrt{3} \gamma_{M1}} \quad (2)$$

$$\chi_w = \begin{cases} \eta & \text{for } \lambda_w \leq 0.65/\eta \\ 0.65/\lambda_w & \text{for } 0.65/\eta < \lambda_w < 0.65 \\ 1.56/(0.91 + \lambda_w) & \text{for } \lambda_w \geq 0.65 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

In Eq. (3), the parameter λ_w corresponds to the web slenderness, as defined by Eq. (4) for webs with transverse stiffeners at both supports and mid-span. The parameter ε represents the material factor and k_τ represents the coefficient associated with web shear buckling. The material factor (ε) is determined using Eq. (5), and the coefficient (k_τ) for web shear buckling in plates with rigid transverse stiffeners and without longitudinal stiffeners is presented in Eq. (6). These equations include parameters like yield strength (f_y), modulus of elasticity (E), and the spacing between transverse stiffeners (a).

$$\lambda_w = \frac{h_w}{37.4 t_w \varepsilon \sqrt{k_\tau}} \quad (4)$$

$$\varepsilon = \sqrt{\frac{235}{f_y} \cdot \frac{E}{210000}} \quad (5)$$

$$k_\tau = \begin{cases} 5.34 + \frac{4}{(a/h_w)^2} & \text{for } a/h_w \geq 1 \\ 4 + \frac{5.34}{(a/h_w)^2} & \text{for } a/h_w < 1 \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

3.2 Proposed EN1993-1-4 (17) shear design guidelines by Dissanayake et al. (18)

Dissanayake et al. (18) assessed the effectiveness of the current shear design provisions for CFSS sections. The shear design guidelines as discussed in Section 3.1 were assessed against the shear tests and parametric FEA results of CFSS lipped channels. The comparison of results demonstrated that current shear design provisions are not suitable and too conservative to estimate the shear strength of CFSS lipped channels. Fig. 5 shows the comparison of the experimental and FEA results with current shear design curve. Dissanayake et al. (18) reported that the primary reason for this deviation is the

strength enhancement observed in compact sections, attributed to the strain hardening effect of stainless steel.

Fig. 5. Comparison of the experimental and FEA shear strengths with the current shear design curve (18)

In order to overcome these limitations, Dissanayake et al. (18) suggested revisions to the shear design guidelines to enhance the prediction accuracy. A series of equations were introduced to define the web shear buckling coefficient (χ_w) as function of web slenderness. When dealing with sections that experience failure below their yield load, a different equation was proposed. Similarly, for sections exhibiting greater strength beyond their yield load due to the notable strain hardening effect of stainless steel, a separate equation was suggested. This latter equation also incorporated an upper limit. The modified web shear buckling coefficient ($\chi_{w,new}$) proposed by Dissanayake et al. (18) is presented in Eq. (7). The comparison of the experimental and finite element analysis results with the proposed shear design curve is depicted in Fig. 6. The proposed equations improved the accuracy of predictions, particularly within the compact zone in the web slenderness region, highlighting their effectiveness in accurately capturing the inelastic reserve capacity and strain hardening found in shear for CFSS lipped channels.

$$\chi_{w,new} = \begin{cases} 2.1 & \text{for } \lambda_w \leq 0.12 \\ 0.839/\lambda_w^{0.433} & \text{for } 0.12 < \lambda_w < 0.667 \\ 1.797/(1.13 + \lambda_w) & \text{for } \lambda_w \geq 0.667 \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

Fig. 6. Comparison of the experimental and FEA shear strengths with the proposed shear design curve (18)

4 NEW SHEAR DESIGN PROPOSALS FOR CFSS LIPPED CHANNELS WITH WEB HOLES

4.1 New design equations

The existing EN1993-1-4 (17) standard does not offer guidance for estimating the shear strength of CFSS lipped channels containing web holes. Although the improved shear design guidelines proposed by Dissanayake et al. (18) for CFSS lipped channels did not incorporate consideration for web holes, Ishqy et al. (1) developed a conventional reduction factor-based approach to capture the influence of circular web holes in CFSS lipped channels. However, this proposed design method by Ishqy et al. (1) is not in line with the EN1993-1-4 (17) guidelines. Dissanayake et al. (18) proposed improved shear design guidelines for CFSS lipped channels without web holes in line with EN1993-1-4 (17). Based on the collected data in Section 2, Dissanayake et al.'s (18) shear design guidelines have been extended in this Section to account for the impact of web holes in CFSS lipped channels. Fig. 7 depicts the compiled FEA data graphed alongside the shear design curve proposed by Dissanayake et al. (18), disregarding the influence of web holes. The data without web holes demonstrates a favourable alignment with the shear design curve, while data incorporating circular web holes indicates a conservative prediction that becomes increasingly conservative as the size of the circular web holes increases.

A simple modification can be made to improve the prediction accuracy of the EN1993-1-4 (17) shear design guidelines for CFSS lipped channels with circular web holes. This modification involves understanding how web holes affect the situation, causing the web slenderness to increase due to their presence. Consequently, the web slenderness Eq. (4) was modified replacing the thickness of the web (t_w) with equivalent thickness of the web ($t_{w,eq}$) for the case of circular web holes. A new equation for equivalent thickness was proposed as a function of web hole ratio. The equivalent thickness of the web ($t_{w,eq}$) also accounts for Equation (2) when estimating shear resistance. The proposed equivalent thickness of the web ($t_{w,eq}$) is presented in Eq. (8).

$$t_{w,eq} = [(1 - R^{1.43})^{0.72}]t_w \quad (8)$$

Fig. 7. Comparison of the experimental and finite element analysis shear strengths with the proposed shear design curve by Dissanayake et al. (18)

Here, R denotes the web hole ratio which is the ratio between web hole height and clear height of the web. It is worth noting that the proposed equivalent thickness is only valid for web hole ratios from 0.1 to 0.85 and only suitable for CFSS lipped channels with circular web holes. It's important to

highlight that when $R=0$, signifying the absence of web holes, *Eq. (8)* converges to t_w . Therefore, the proposed approach can be used to estimate the shear strength of CFSS lipped channels without and with circular web holes.

4.2 Assessment of new design equations

Fig. 8 illustrates the compiled data for CFS beams containing web holes, graphed against the shear design curve using the proposed equivalent thickness approach. In contrast to *Fig. 7*, *Fig. 8* exhibits a more pronounced agreement between the data points and the proposed EN1993-14 shear design guidelines by Dissanayake et al. (18). The comparison of shear strength prediction from the proposed equations considering equivalent thickness approach and collected FEA data is demonstrated in *Fig. 9*. This comparison revealed an average ratio of 1.00 and coefficient of variation (COV) of 0.072. This outcome signifies accuracy and consistency in estimating shear strength of CFSS lipped channels with web holes. As part of future research, the authors aim to conduct a reliability analysis of the proposed shear design provisions, with the goal of enhancing their comprehensiveness and practicality.

Fig. 8. FEA data for CFSS lipped channels with circular web holes, plotted using the proposed equivalent thickness approach.

Fig. 9. Comparison between shear strength predictions derived from the proposed equivalent thickness approach and the FEA data collected.

5 CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents an investigation of cold-formed stainless steel (CFSS) lipped channels with circular web holes under predominant shear force. The study utilizes shear numerical data collected from existing literature to assess the effectiveness of the current shear design guidelines outlined in EN 1993-1-4 (17). The dataset comprises various CFSS lipped channels and circular web holes of different sizes. The collected shear strength data with circular web holes were compared against the improved shear design guidelines for CFSS lipped channels proposed by Dissanayake et al. (18). It was observed that the existing shear design guidelines did not account for the influence of web holes, resulting in conservative shear strength predictions. To address these limitations, novel shear design guidelines were proposed based on a new equivalent thickness approach to consider circular web holes. These proposals incorporate the adoption of a modified web slenderness through an equivalent thickness approach within the recently proposed shear design guidelines developed by Dissanayake et al. (18). The proposed shear design guidelines, in line with EN 1993-1-4 (17) standards, demonstrated greater accuracy and consistency in predicting the shear strength of CFSS lipped channels with circular web holes, covering web hole ratios ranging from 0.1 to 0.85.

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